

MODELING BIAXIAL-TENSION COUPLING IN WOVEN FABRIC

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ABSTRACT

An nonlinear anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive model is developed for woven fabrics by considering biaxial tensile coupling. The strain energy function of the developed constitutive model is decomposed into three parts to represent the tensile energy from fiber elongation, shearing energy from interaction between warp and weft yarns, and finally compaction energy due to biaxial tensile coupling in the two fiber yarn directions, respectively. The model is exemplified on a specific balanced plain woven fabric. Experimental data from literature are used to identify material parameters in the constitutive model. Model validation is implemented by comparing numerical results with various experimental data including biaxial tension under different stretch ratios, picture-frame shearing and hemispherical stamping. It is demonstrated that the developed constitutive model is suitable to characterize the highly non-linear and strongly anisotropic mechanical behaviors of woven fabrics under large deformation. The proposed model provides a theoretical foundation for the numerical simulation and processing optimization of woven composites forming.

1 INTRODUCTION

Textile composites have many superior mechanical properties, such as high specific strength and specific stiffness, good corrosion resistance, fatigue properties and so on [1]. However, their high manufacturing cost, immature structure design and process analysis methods have become the bottlenecks in mass production applications of the automobile and other civilian industries [2]. In recent years, stamping of woven composites is approved to be a highly efficient process for realizing automation of production, achieving mass production and expanding the application range of woven fabrics in auto industry [3-6]. However, the stamping process of woven composites involves large deformation, nonlinear and anisotropy of the fabric, so developing a suitable constitutive model to characterize the mechanical properties of woven fabrics is important to theoretical significance and engineering application.

There exist kinematic method, discrete method and continuous method for forming analysis of woven composites. The kinematic or fishnet model cannot give the information on the mechanical behavior of the fabric [7-8]. The discrete models or meso-scale models can provide the details on stress distribution in the yarns and changes of geometry, rotation and slippage of the yarns during forming process [9-12]. Nevertheless, compared with continuous method, computational cost of the discrete method is higher. The continuous models regard fibrous material as a continuum in average at macroscopic scale and can be easily combined with standard finite element codes. In the past a hypoelastic law was often used to model the deformation of unit cell including only one direction fibers at mesoscopic scale. Then this hypoelastic law was extended to the macroscopic level where have two fiber directions in the forming simulation in Badel et al. [13] and Khan et al. [14]. Despite of wide application of a hypoelastic constitutive model, this law is only suitable for characterizing small elastic deformation, since for large deformation the work done in a closed deformation path is not zero necessarily. In addition, in order to characterize the anisotropic material behavior of woven fabrics under large deformation Peng and Cao [15] developed a non-orthogonal constitutive model which can track the reorientation of the weft and warp yarns and validated the rationality of this model through bias extension test and shear test. Then Peng and Rehman [16] successfully employed this non-orthogonal model to simulate the anisotropic mechanical behavior of textile composites under large deformation during stamping. Lee et al. [17] further developed the tension-shear coupled non-orthogonal accounting for the effects of tensions in yarns on the shear behavior of woven fabric and

validated the accuracy of this coupled model though uniaxial and biaxial tensile test and double dome stretching test. However, the determination of the materials parameters of the coupled non-orthogonal constitutive model are difficult and its range of application is limited. Since a hyperelastic model can avoid the drawback of a hypoelastic model that energy is not conserved for large deformations, now anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive models are increasingly being used to simulate the large elastic deformation of strongly anisotropic materials, e.g. reinforced rubber-like materials [18, 19], biological tissues [20-21] and woven textile fabrics [22-24].

Usually, for simplicity, most constitutive models for woven fabric did not consider the coupling phenomena in the forming process such as biaxial tensile coupling and tension-shear coupling behavior. However, experimental results showed that these coupling phenomena are existent [12, 25]. In order to improve the accuracy of a numerical simulation, some models had taken into account the probably existing couplings. Boisse et al. [9-10, 12] employed a hyperelastic model at a meso scale, and Lee et al. [17, 26] used a hypoelastic law at a macro scale to consider the the biaxial tensile coupling. In addition,

The biaxial tension-tension coupling here would mean that applying tension on a given family of yarns changes the tensile ‘rigidity’ (modulus) of the other family of yarns through meso-level mechanisms such as increase in crimping, increase in contact force and so on. In this paper, an anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive model at a macro scale for dry fabrics considering biaxial-tension coupling is developed through introducing compaction energy due to biaxial tensile coupling in the warp and weft direction. The material parameters of the constitutive model are determined by fitting the experimental uniaxial tension, equi-biaxial tension and picture shear data. The developed model is validated by comparing numerical results with experimental data of biaxial tension data under different stretch ratios, picture-frame shearing and hemispherical stamping, demonstrating that the developed constitutive model is accuracy and reliability.

2 ANISOTROPIC HYPERELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL WITH BIAxIAL-TENSION COUPLING FOR WOVEN FABRICS

2.1 General format for the constitutive model

A stored strain energy function based on phenomenon for a hyperelastic material which is anisotropic with respect to the initial unstressed configuration is defined to describe the macroscopic mechanical properties of the woven fabrics according to the continuum mechanics theory. The strain energy function W can be expressed as a scalar function of the initial fiber directional unit vectors for weft yarns \mathbf{a}_0 and warp yarns \mathbf{b}_0 and the right Cauchy-Green strain tensor \mathbf{C} . Alternatively, the strain energy can be expressed as a scalar function of the principal invariants I_i ($i=1,\dots,9$) of the right Cauchy-Green strain tensor [27], i.e.,

$$W = W(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0) = W(I_i) \quad (i=1,\dots,9) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}$ is the right Cauchy-Green strain tensor. $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \partial \mathbf{x} / \partial \mathbf{X}$ is the deformation gradient tensor. \mathbf{X} represents the position of a material particle in the original configuration, while \mathbf{x} is the position of the corresponding particle in the current configuration. The principal invariants are defined as,

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}), \quad I_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[(\text{tr} \mathbf{C})^2 - \text{tr}(\mathbf{C}^2) \right] \\ I_3 &= \det(\mathbf{C}), \quad I_4 = \mathbf{A}_0 : \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{a}_0 = \lambda_a^2 \\ I_5 &= \mathbf{A}_0 : \mathbf{C}^2 = \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \mathbf{a}_0, \quad I_6 = \mathbf{C}_0 : \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{b}_0 \\ I_7 &= \mathbf{C}_0 : \mathbf{C}^2 = \mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \mathbf{b}_0, \quad I_8 = \mathbf{B}_0 : \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{b}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{b}_0 = \lambda_b^2 \\ I_9 &= \mathbf{B}_0 : \mathbf{C}^2 = \mathbf{b}_0 \cdot \mathbf{C}^2 \cdot \mathbf{b}_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_0 = \mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0$, $\mathbf{B}_0 = \mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0$ and $\mathbf{C}_0 = \mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0$ are structure tensors. λ_a and λ_b are the stretch ratios of the weft and warp fiber yarns, respectively.

The second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{S} obtained directly from the strain energy function W is

$$\mathbf{S} = 2 \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^9 \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial I_i} \frac{\partial I_i}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \right) \quad (3)$$

The Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = J^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T = 2J^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{F} \cdot \left[\sum_{i=1}^9 \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial I_i} \frac{\partial I_i}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \right) \right] \cdot \mathbf{F}^T \quad (4)$$

where $J = \det(\mathbf{F}) = \sqrt{I_3}$ is the Jacobian representing the ratio of an infinitesimal volume in the deformed body to the corresponding volume of the segment in the undeformed body. Since the balanced plain weave fabric researched in this paper is high density, there are less voids in the material [28]. The assumption of incompressibility will be reasonable (i.e. $J = 1$). $\frac{\partial I_i}{\partial \mathbf{C}}$ is first-order derivative of the principal invariants of a second-order strain tensor with respect to the tensor itself.

2.2 Decoupling of strain energy for woven fabric

The main deformation modes of woven fabric in the process of forming are the elongations along the fiber directions, the compaction in the transverse section of the yarns, shear deformation in the transverse section and bending deformation [12]. Generally, the bending stiffness of the fibers is very small. Thus it can be neglected. The strain energy per unit volume of the hyperelastic model is additively decomposed into three parts, representing the tensile energy from fiber elongation, compaction energy due to biaxial tensile coupling in the warp and weft direction and shearing energy from interaction between warp and weft yarns,

$$W(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{a}_0, \mathbf{b}_0) = W_{Tension} + W_{Compaction} + W_{Shear} \quad (5)$$

2.2.1 Elongation strain energy

The invariant I_4 is employed to indicate the stretch state of the warp yarns. Obviously, fiber is in the undeformed state if $I_4 = 1$, experiences extension if $I_4 > 1$ and compression if $I_4 < 1$. Thus, the elongation strain energy from stretch of warp yarns can be written as a scalar function of the principal invariant I_4 . Because of very weak resistance to compressive loads compared to tensile loads, fibers are assumed to have no compressive stiffness. The tensile response of fibers can be very well characterized by the exponential function dependent on I_4 [23]. Consequently, the elongation strain energy from stretch of warp yarns $W_{F_a}(I_4)$ is

$$W_{F_a}(I_4) = \begin{cases} \frac{c_{1a}}{2c_{2a}} \left\{ \exp\left[c_{2a}(I_4 - 1)^2 \right] - 1 \right\} & I_4 \geq 1 \\ 0 & I_4 < 1 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The elongation strain energy from stretch of weft yarns $W_{F_b}(I_8)$ has the same functional format as that of $W_{F_a}(I_4)$

$$W_{F_b}(I_8) = \begin{cases} \frac{c_{1b}}{2c_{2b}} \left\{ \exp[c_{2b}(I_8 - 1)^2] - 1 \right\} & I_8 \geq 1 \\ 0 & I_8 < 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where c_{1a} and c_{1b} are material parameters with a unit of MPa. c_{2a} and c_{2b} are dimensionless material parameters. Finally, the elongation strain energy $W_{Tension}$ from stretches of yarns including both warp and weft directions is

$$W_{Tension}(I_4, I_8) = W_{F_a}(I_4) + W_{F_b}(I_8) \quad (8)$$

2.2.2 Compaction strain energy

Biaxial tensile coupling in the warp and weft directions can produce the compaction in the transverse section of the yarns. Therefore the compaction strain energy depends on the elongation of fibers and the warp/weft tensile ratio. The compaction strain energy from the elongation of warp yarns, $W_{C_a}(I_4)$ can be defined as

$$W_{C_a}(I_4) = \begin{cases} f(R_1) \left[\sum_{i=2}^4 k_{ia} (I_4 - 1)^i \right] & I_4 \geq 1 \text{ and } I_8 \geq 1 \\ 0 & I_4 < 1 \text{ or } I_8 < 1 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The compaction strain energy from elongation of weft yarns $W_{C_b}(I_8)$ has the same functional format as that of $W_{C_a}(I_4)$

$$W_{C_b}(I_8) = \begin{cases} f(R_2) \left[\sum_{i=2}^4 k_{jb} (I_8 - 1)^i \right] & I_4 \geq 1 \text{ and } I_8 \geq 1 \\ 0 & I_4 < 1 \text{ or } I_8 < 1 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where k_{ia} and k_{jb} are material parameters with a unit of MPa. Based on experimental observation [12], the influence factors $f(R_1)$ and $f(R_2)$ are expressed as

$$f(R_1) = \frac{(\alpha + 1)R_1^\beta}{\alpha + R_1^\beta}, \quad f(R_2) = \frac{(\alpha + 1)R_2^\beta}{\alpha + R_2^\beta} \quad (11)$$

where α and β are dimensionless material parameters. R_1 represents tensile ratio of the weft fiber to the warp fiber while R_2 represents tensile ratio of the warp fiber to the weft fiber, and

$R_1 = R_2^{-1} = \varepsilon_{22} / \varepsilon_{11}$. Finally the compaction strain energy $W_{Compaction}$ from stretch of yarns including both warp and weft directions is

$$W_{Compaction}(I_4, I_8) = W_{C_a}(I_4) + W_{C_b}(I_8) \quad (12)$$

2.2.3 Shear strain energy

There are many different forms of shear invariants in the previous literature [22, 29]. Here the variation of the angle between the warp and weft yarns (i.e. shear angle) is employed to define shear invariant I_{10}

$$I_{10} = -\arccos \left[\left(I_4 I_8 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} I_6 \right] + \arccos(\mathbf{a}_0 \cdot \mathbf{b}_0) \quad (13)$$

A polynomial function of the principal invariants I_{10} is chosen to describe the shear strain energy

W_{Shear}

$$W_{Shear}(I_4, I_6, I_8) = W_{FF}(I_{10}) = \sum_{i=2}^4 s_i (I_{10})^i \quad (14)$$

where $s_i (i = 2, \dots, 4)$ are shear parameters with a unit of MPa.

2.3 Anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive model for woven fabrics

In the previous sections, elongation strain energy, compaction strain energy and shear strain energy have been determined respectively and these functions possess clear physical meaning. The second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor \mathbf{S} can be obtained by substituting (5) ~ (14) into (3)

$$\mathbf{S} = 2 \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial I_4} \frac{\partial I_4}{\partial \mathbf{C}} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_8} \frac{\partial I_8}{\partial \mathbf{C}} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_6} \frac{\partial I_6}{\partial \mathbf{C}} \right) \quad (15)$$

where $\frac{\partial I_i}{\partial \mathbf{C}}$ are

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial I_4}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0, & \frac{\partial I_8}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0 \\ \frac{\partial I_6}{\partial \mathbf{C}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{I_4 I_8 - I_6^2}} \left[\mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0 - \frac{I_6}{2} \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0}{I_4} + \frac{\mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0}{I_8} \right) \right] \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Through substituting (16) into (15), using W_i to represent $\frac{\partial W}{\partial I_i}$ the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor

\mathbf{S} is as below

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{S} = & 2(W_4 \mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0 + W_8 \mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0) \\ & + \frac{W_{10}}{\sqrt{I_4 I_8 - I_6^2}} \left[\mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0 + \mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0 - I_6 \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}_0 \otimes \mathbf{a}_0}{I_4} + \frac{\mathbf{b}_0 \otimes \mathbf{b}_0}{I_8} \right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Finally, substituting (17) into (4), the Cauchy stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ can be obtained.

By decomposing the hyperelastic strain energy into three independent parts and utilizing experimental methods including uniaxial tension, biaxial tension and picture-frame shear test, the material parameters of the constitutive model can be determined easily. The procedure for determining these parameters is given as follows.

- (1) By matching experimental data of uni-axial tensile tests along one fiber yarn direction, the parameters of elongation strain energy c_{ia} and c_{ib} can be determined.
- (2) By matching experimental data of equal-biaxial tensile tests, the parameters of compaction strain energy α , β , k_{ia} and k_{ib} can obtain.
- (3) By matching experimental data of picture-frame test to obtain the shear parameters of shear strain energy s_i .

3 DETERMINATION OF MATERIAL PARAMETERS

A balanced plain glass woven fabric tested in [12] is taken as an example to demonstrate the constitutive modeling process. Experimental testing results from [12] are used to determine the material parameters of the proposed constitutive model.

Figure 1: Experimental data and curve fitting: (a) Biaxial tension curves from experiment and simulation, (b) Tensile strain energy density versus $I_4 - 1$ in uni-axial tensile test, (c) Compaction strain energy density versus $I_4 - 1$ in equi-biaxial and uneven biaxial tensile test, (d) Shear strain energy density versus shear angle in picture frame test.

3.1 Parameters of elongation strain energy

The experimental uniaxial tensile load-displacement curve in Fig. 1(a) and the geometrical parameters of the fabric [12] are used to obtain the $W_{Fa} - (I_4 - 1)$ curves. Then through nonlinear curve fitting as shown in Fig. 1(b), the parameters of elongation strain energy W_{Fa} are

$$c_{1a} = c_{1b} = 15.12 \text{ MPa}, \quad c_{2a} = c_{2b} = 10000.24 \text{ MPa} \quad (18)$$

3.2 Parameters of compaction strain energy

When woven fabric is subjected to uni-axial tension in the warp direction (i.e. $\varepsilon_{22} = 0$), $f(R_1)$ and $W_{Ca}(I_4)$ in Eq. (9) become 0.0, therefore there is no compaction energy under the uni-axial load. When woven fabric is subjected to equi-biaxial tension, R_1 and $f(R_1)$ become 1.0, therefore the parameters k_{ia} in Eq. (9) can be determined by fitting the experimental $W_{Ca}(I_4) - (I_4 - 1)$ curve of $R_1 = 1$ (i.e. equi-biaxial tension). Then α and β are obtained by fitting the experimental $W_{Ca}(I_4) - (I_4 - 1)$ curve of $R_1 = 2$ or $R_1 = 0.5$. Finally, α , β and k_{ia} are further adjusted so that the fitting curves fit well with the three experimental curves simultaneously, as shown in Fig. 1(c). The parameters of compaction strain energy can be determined as

$$\begin{aligned} k_{2a} = k_{2b} = -10 \text{ MPa}, \quad k_{3a} = k_{3b} = 51000 \text{ MPa}, \quad k_{4a} = k_{4b} = -1 \times 10^5 \text{ MPa} \\ \alpha = 4, \quad \beta = 2.0 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

3.3 Parameters of shear strain energy

Torque per unit initial area - shear angle experimental curve of the picture-frame test in [12] is used to obtain the experimental $W_{Shear} - I_{10}$ curve. Then through nonlinear curve fitting as shown in Fig. 1(d), the parameters of shear strain energy W_{Shear} are

$$s_2 = 0.068 \text{ MPa}, s_3 = 0.035 \text{ MPa}, s_4 = 0.020 \text{ MPa} \quad (20)$$

4 MODEL VALIDATION AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the proposed hyperelastic constitutive law is combined with the standard finite element software ABAQUS by developing user material subroutine *uanisohyper_inv*. Then biaxial tension under different stretch ratios, picture-frame shearing and hemispherical stamping are simulated using the developed finite element codes. Finally, model validation is implemented by comparing numerical results with experimental data.

4.1 Biaxial tensile test

Figure 2(a) shows FE model of the biaxial tension for woven fabrics. The effective size of the fabric is $50\text{mm} \times 50\text{mm} \times 0.80\text{mm}$ and the element type is S4R. It should be noted that S4R elements means that bending stiffness is directly proportional to tensile stiffness. It is not consistent with the assumption that bending stiffness is negligible. Nevertheless, the bending energy caused by the tension of shell element S4R is still negligible compared to the other three energies mentioned in equation (5) for the following three numerical simulation tests. In other hand, neglecting bending stiffness for S4R shell element will cause numerical instability. Fortunately, this problem can be solved by defining transverse shear stiffness in ABAQUS input file. In Fig. 1(a), solid lines with squares represent simulation results of biaxial tension under different stretch ratios, while hollow circles represent corresponding experimental data. Generally, The simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental data. In other hand, without considering the biaxial coupling effect (i.e. using non-biaxial model), the simulation results of biaxial tension under different stretch ratios represented by black stars in Fig. 1(a) are all the same and close to the uniaxial tensile testing data as shown in Fig. 1(a), which indicates that considering the biaxial coupling effect is necessary in developing the constitutive model.

4.2 Picture frame test

Figure 2(b) shows the FE model of the picture frame test for woven fabrics. The effective size of the fabric is $140\text{mm} \times 140\text{mm} \times 0.80\text{mm}$ and the element type is S4R. In order to avoid elongation and compaction deformation due to misalignment of fiber yarns in the frame, multiple-point constrains are implemented on the four picture frames to ensure that only the shear deformation mode exists in the numerical test. The shear strain energy-shear angle curves are shown in Fig. 1(d) by solid squares. It is indicated in Fig. 1(d) that the numerical results are in good agreement with the experimental data for picture frame testing. Therefore, the shear parameters obtained from curve-fitting are accurate.

Figure 2: Numerical test of (a) biaxial tension and (b) picture frame.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on continuum mechanics theory, an anisotropic hyperelastic constitutive model with biaxial tension coupling is developed to characterize the large deformation, nonlinear and anisotropic mechanical behavior of woven fabric during forming process. The strain energy per unit volume of the proposed hyperelastic model is additively decomposed into tensile energy, compaction energy and shearing energy respectively, which greatly facilitates the determination of material parameters. Then the processes of determining parameters are given clearly. Finally, the proposed anisotropic hyperelastic model is applied to simulate biaxial tension, picture-frame shear test and hemispherical stamping. Numerical results are compared with corresponding experimental data indicating that the model is validate and accurate. The developed constitutive model has the advantages of higher preision, stronger practicability and easier determination of material parameters. Therefore, it provides a theoretical foundation for the numerical simulation and processing optimization of woven composites forming in the future.

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